

The Level of Organizational Excellence within Public Hospitals from Doctors' Perspective: A Field Study at Brothers Ben Toubel Hospital- Mila

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the level of organizational excellence at the Brothers Ben Toubel Hospital in Mila from the doctors' perspective. A descriptive approach was utilized, and the study population consisted of 47 doctors, including 18 general practitioners and 29 specialists. A comprehensive survey method was employed for the sample study, and a questionnaire was used as a data collection tool. The results indicated that the level of organizational excellence is high at the Brothers Ben Toubel Hospital in Mila. There were no statistically significant differences in organizational excellence levels between genders (male/female). However, significant differences were found between general practitioners and specialists regarding the level of organizational excellence

Keywords: *Organizational Excellence; Leadership Excellence; Human Resource Excellence; Planning Excellence; Doctors.*

INTRODUCTION

In light of changes, developments, and increasing competition intensity, organizations strive to adopt a set of modern managerial tools and concepts that provide new elements to preserve and propel them towards competition with other organizations. (Hijazi and Tanbour, 2018, p.135)

Many organizations, especially health organizations, face numerous problems due to their management's failure to keep up with modern and contemporary management methods used by global organizations. This, coupled with the rapid pace of development in this area and our organizations' slow response, has led to deteriorating performance, particularly in the level of services provided to patients, negatively affecting the medical services delivery and other services in health organizations in our country. (Nadia Lotfi and Sanaa Mahmoud, n.d., p.421)

One of the concepts that can help these organizations compete and keep up with rapid developments is the concept of excellence. Achieving a state of excellence is not easy; it is a continuous and ongoing effort at all organizational levels. Health organizations face significant challenges, with client expectations rising, leading to a constant search for optimal health service quality. Thus, seeking organizational excellence has become a necessary demand within hospitals.

1.Study Problem

Organizational excellence represents the accumulation of continuous efforts that lead to competitive advantage, allowing organizations to compete with leaders in their field, meet their needs and those of their workers and customers, and increase satisfaction levels among all parties.

Organizational excellence in Algerian hospitals is a significant research area, being a crucial principle for the survival and development of any hospital, and providing an opportunity to adapt to the surrounding environment through constant changes. Given the above, it was justified to explore the level of organizational excellence within public hospitals from the doctors' perspective, leading to the following question:

What is the level of organizational excellence within public hospitals?

There are several related questions:

- Are there statistically significant differences in the level of organizational excellence among doctors at Ben Toubel Hospital attributed to gender?
- Are there statistically significant differences in the level of organizational excellence among doctors at Ben Toubel Hospital attributed to the specialization variable (general practitioner/specialist) ?

2. Study Hypotheses

2.1 General Hypothesis

- The level of organizational excellence is high at Ben Toubel Hospital in Mila.

2.2 Specific Hypotheses

- There are no statistically significant differences in the level of organizational excellence at Ben Toubel Hospital from the perspective attributed to gender.
- There are no statistically significant differences in the level of organizational excellence at Ben Toubel Hospital from doctors' perspectives attributed to the specialization variable (general practitioner/specialist).

3. Significance Of The Study

The importance of the study stems from the significance of services in hospitals and healthcare for patients, making the delivery of services characterized by excellence a necessary and important matter as it is linked to human life. Therefore, the study's importance is reflected in the following aspects:

- Introducing excellence as a modern and contemporary organizational and administrative element.
- Keeping pace with developments in global health institutions that have achieved a high level of organizational excellence at all levels.
- Encouraging administrative leaders in hospitals to adopt an excellence management policy according to international standards.
- Opening the field for researchers to conduct further studies on organizational excellence in hospitals.

4. Study Objectives

This study aims to:

- Determine the level of organizational excellence within public hospitals.
- Examine the presence of statistically significant differences in the level of organizational excellence among doctors at Ben Toubel Hospital attributed to gender.

- Examine the presence of statistically significant differences in the level of organizational excellence among doctors at Ben Toubel Hospital attributed to years of service.

5. Operational Definitions Of Study Terms

5.1 Organizational Excellence

The result of applying a set of standards that help institutions achieve high competitive outcomes, aiding in their goal achievement.

5.2 Leadership Excellence

One of the necessary excellence standards in institutions, where a successful leader motivates and drives their team to achieve a high level of excellence.

5.3 Planning Excellence

A necessary process in institutions aimed at identifying future plans and actions for achieving their goals.

5.4 Human Resource Excellence

Represents the efficiency and skills of subordinates within the organization and their ability to achieve a distinguished performance level that helps the institution achieve its goals.

5.5 Customer Focus

Reflected in the hospital management's emphasis on the comfort of the client (patients) and attention to their needs, an essential element in any institution's excellence.

6. Study Limits

6.1 Subjective Limits: The level of organizational excellence in public hospitals.

6.2 Spatial Limits: The Brothers Ben Toubel Hospital in Mila.

6.3 Human Limits: Doctors at the Brothers Ben Toubel Hospital in Mila.

6.4 Temporal Limits: The academic year 2023/2024.

7. Previous Studies

7.1 Study by Ali Mohammed Said Al-Ali 2016

Requirements for Achieving Organizational Excellence in Secondary Schools in Taif Governorate from Their Leaders' Perspective"

The study aimed to identify the requirements for achieving organizational excellence in secondary schools in Taif Governorate from their leaders' perspective, using a descriptive survey method and relying on a questionnaire as the primary data collection tool. The questionnaire consisted of 35 items, distributed across five dimensions (school leadership, strategic planning, organizational structure, human resource management, organizational culture). The study sample included 108 school leaders.

The results showed that the requirements for organizational excellence, overall, were deemed very important from the leaders' perspective. The dimensions were ranked as follows: organizational culture, school leadership, human resource management, strategic planning, organizational structure, all with very high importance.

The research revealed no differences in the average responses of secondary school leaders regarding the requirements for achieving organizational excellence. (Said Al-Ali, 2016)

7.2 Study by Reem Ahmad Saleh Al-Ghamdi 2018

"Organizational Excellence among Leaders in the Al-Baha Region from Teachers' Perspective"

The study aimed to identify the degree of organizational excellence among school leaders in the Al-Baha region from the teachers' perspective, using a descriptive survey method. The study sample consisted of 4146 teachers, with a subset of 345 teachers from schools in the Al-Baha region selected randomly. A questionnaire with 50 items was used for data collection.

The results showed that the study sample rated the degree of organizational excellence among school leaders in the Al-Baha region as very high. There were differences in organizational excellence based on the educational qualification variable, favoring those with higher degrees. (Al-Ghamdi, 2018)

7.3 Study by Ruba Ezzat Al-Kanj 2020

"The Availability of Organizational Excellence Dimensions in Service Organizations: A Field Study in Syriatel Company"

This research aimed to determine the availability of organizational excellence dimensions (leadership, human resources, customer satisfaction, employee satisfaction, service quality, process quality) in service organizations, applied to Syriatel Company in Latakia Governorate. The study, adopting a descriptive analytical approach, included Syriatel employees, totaling approximately 132 workers. A questionnaire was distributed as the data collection tool, with 126 responses retrieved.

The results showed that the level of organizational excellence in the studied company was high, with all sub-dimensions of excellence receiving relatively high and close importance, the highest being customer satisfaction and the lowest being process quality. (Al-Kanj, 2020)

7.4 Study by Ahmed Jassim and Khalaf Taha (2022)

"Measuring Organizational Excellence among Primary School Principals"

The study aimed to determine the level of organizational excellence among primary school principals and identify differences in organizational excellence based on gender (male, female) and years of service. The study sample consisted of 350 principals, using a descriptive method suitable for the study and a questionnaire for data collection.

The results showed that school principals have a high level of organizational excellence, with the female segment of the study sample showing a higher level of organizational excellence than males. Regarding the years of service variable, the results indicated that principals with less than 5 years of service had a higher degree of organizational excellence than those with more than 6 years of experience. (Ahmed Jassim and Khalaf Taha, 2022)

7.5 Study by Reem Mohammed Al-Sheet and Asmaa Al-Khayyat (2023)

"Organizational Excellence among Department Heads at the University of Mosul According to Variables from Teachers' Perspective"

This study aimed to determine the organizational excellence among department heads at the University of Mosul from the teachers' perspective. The research relied on a questionnaire

for information collection and a descriptive method suitable for the study. The study sample consisted of 381 individuals randomly selected, representing 10% of the study population. The results showed:

- The level of organizational excellence was higher than the hypothetical average for department heads at the University of Mosul from the teachers' perspective.
- There was a statistically significant difference attributed to the academic title variable (assistant lecturer/assistant professor) in the level of organizational excellence among department heads at the University of Mosul from the teachers' perspective, in favor of the assistant professor. (Al-Sheet and Al-Khayyat, 2023)

7.6 Comments on Previous Studies

After reviewing previous studies, we observed that most aimed to understand the level of organizational excellence, aligning with our study. However, a noticeable difference lies in the study sample or the sector in which the studies were conducted. Most were in the educational and economic sectors, unlike our study, which is in the healthcare sector. Studies on organizational excellence in the healthcare sector are scarce or almost non-existent.

Our current study agrees with previous ones in using a descriptive approach and questionnaires as data collection tools. The benefit from previous studies lies in understanding organizational excellence across different fields and considering the results of these studies as a starting point for ours, despite the difference in our study's domain, where research on organizational excellence in Algerian hospitals is scarce, if not absent.

8. Theoretical Framework

8.1. Definition of Organizational Excellence

The European Foundation for Quality Management (EFQM) defines it as "the outstanding practice in managing the organization and achieving results that satisfy various stakeholders, including customers, employees, shareholders, and the community at large... etc.

Outstanding practice extends to a range of factors such as leadership that formulates and directs policies, strategies, human and financial resources, various internal processes, information systems, and more." (Ahlam Kirkuk, 2021)

Al-Quraioti (2000) defined it as "excellence from the perspective of focusing on creative results, as the second approach to studying creativity, represented by the amount of productivity and brilliance in performance."

And Bassam (2005) described it as "behavior (performance) that exceeds the average standard performance, also representing a link in the chain of superior performance." (Hassouni, n.d., p.213)

From these definitions, we can say that excellence is a set of continuous and concerted efforts at all levels to become better in everything from improving human resource performance, accurately setting strategies, enhancing organizational culture, developing leaders, etc., to gain a distinguished position among competitors and satisfy its customers.

8.2. Importance of Organizational Excellence

The importance of organizational excellence is highlighted in the following points:

- Enhancing the organization's production levels, strengthening the management's relationship with employees, and increasing positive atmosphere among workers.
- The possibility of sustaining and growing, as well as excelling over competitors, achieving creativity, efficiency, quality, better resource utilization, stimulating competitive strengths, and delivering services ideally to satisfy the customer. (Ibrahim Khalid and Al-Kubaisi, 2023, p.598)
- Maintaining the organization's position, as non-excellent performance leads to losing its market status.
- Focusing on quality, as it forms the basis for customers' choices amidst diverse products and services, making quality concern indispensable. (Boudrahm, Salehi, and Tawahir, 2021, p. 217)

The significance of organizational excellence lies in various elements mentioned in most previous studies, emphasizing that organizational excellence is an important and effective factor in raising the general level of the organization and keeping up with significant developments in competing organizations. This is achieved by focusing on the principles of organizational excellence as the direct path to achieving competitive advantage with leading organizations.

Excellence also ensures the continuity and survival of any organization and prevents its disappearance. Moreover, the concept of excellence can be linked to quality, as quality is a mechanism for achieving organizational excellence, ensuring customer satisfaction.

8.3. Dimensions of Organizational Excellence

Leadership Excellence

Refers to distinguished practices adopted by organizations, achieving desired results and supporting the organization's ability to respond flexibly and quickly to changes in its internal and external environment. (Al-Ramadi, Hussein, and Abu Hamad, 2022, p.44)

Human Resource Excellence

Implies that subordinates possess sufficient competencies, skills, and behaviors to perform their jobs effectively, handle workplace situations, and feel a sense of belonging and loyalty. (Rania Wasfi Osman, 2022, p.98)

Organizational Strategy Excellence

Strategy is the mechanism used by an organization to determine its future direction. It involves developing an action plan to mobilize efforts to achieve organizational excellence. The strategy takes the organization forward into the future towards desired goals.

It represents the comprehensive main plan that shows the organization the way to achieve its mission and goals, reflecting excellence through the strategy as the degree of distinction in the steps the organization takes to realize its vision, mission, and interaction as a unified and comprehensive plan that links the organization's strengths, capabilities, and strategic potentials to face complex environmental challenges.

Distinguished organizations execute their mission through a clear strategy reinforced with plans, policies, programs, and their implementation to achieve excellence. (Yousef Mana, 2022, p.09)

Organizational Structure Excellence

Excellence through the organizational structure expresses the structural framework's ability to link the organization's parts, define relationships between jobs, positions, and departments, and clarify lines of authority and responsibility. This enables the performance of various activities and the achievement of desired goals with excellence and distinction.

Organizational Culture Excellence

The organizational culture significantly impacts the performance and achievements of groups and subordinates, largely determining the success and excellence of the institution as a whole. An institution with a weak or negative culture will face failure in the long term regardless of the nature and attractiveness of its activities.

Conversely, a distinguished organizational culture includes shared values, beliefs, and principles among organization members, making communication easier, resulting in better cooperation, commitment, and simplified decision-making processes, thus driving subordinates towards achieving the institution's goals and adhering to organizational excellence standards. (Imran and Brahimia, 2018, p.32)

Knowledge Management

Knowledge management is a set of modern ideas with a significant and effective impact on production success. Its importance comes from being a fundamental component for the success and survival of organizations through its contribution to maintaining and developing a long-term vision as it represents the most value-holding and effective means for competitive advantage for the following reasons:

- Increasing market competition and the speed of new discoveries and innovations, thereby improving customer service.
- Maintaining loyal customers by providing better service to customers.
- Reducing costs and methods of work.

Organizational excellence dimensions are among the most important elements necessary to achieve organizational excellence. They are integrated elements with each other.

For example, the absence of distinguished leadership makes it difficult to achieve human resource excellence and other dimensions, making leadership excellence the primary dimension that achieves the excellence of other dimensions.

9. Applied Aspect

9.1 Methodology

The nature of the study necessitated relying on the descriptive analytical method, as it is most suitable for collecting concepts and facts related to organizational excellence and understanding the nature of the problem through data collection, analysis, and reaching conclusions that contribute to knowing the level of organizational excellence in public hospitals.

The descriptive method is defined as the approach that relies on studying the phenomenon as it exists in reality, interested in describing it accurately, both qualitatively and quantitatively. (Al-Mashhadani, 2019, p.126)

9.2 Study Population

The study population consists of doctors at the Brothers Ben Toubel Hospital in Mila province, totaling 47 doctors divided between general practitioners and specialists. The following table shows the characteristics of the study sample:

Table 01: Characteristics of the Study Sample

Study Sample	Females	Males
General Practitioners	15	3
Specialists	26	3

9.3 Study Tool

The questionnaire developed by the researcher Khalida Ismail Mansour titled "The Impact of Organizational Excellence on the Quality of Health Services in Sudanese Hospitals: Alia Specialized Hospital as a Model" (2021) was used. The questionnaire consists of 20 items distributed across four dimensions as follows:

Table 02: Distribution of Organizational Excellence Scale Dimensions

Variable	Dimension	Number of Items
Organizational Excellence	Leadership Excellence	5 (from 1 to 5)
	Planning Excellence	5 (from 6 to 10)
	Human Resource Excellence	5 (from 11 to 15)
	Customer Focus	5 (from 16 to 20)

9.4 Study Tool Reliability

The study tool was tested using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient to calculate the internal consistency among the questionnaire items. The following table illustrates this:

Table 03: Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient Values for Study Tool Reliability

No.	Dimensions	Number of Statements	Cronbach's Alpha
01	Leadership Excellence	5	0.53
02	Planning Excellence	5	0.63
03	Human Resource Excellence	5	0.55
04	Customer Focus	5	0.75
Organizational Excellence Overall		20	0.87

Table (03) shows the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient values for the study tool, where the value for the organizational excellence measure reached (0.87), indicating a high value. This confirms the reliability of the questionnaire, making it suitable for field application.

10. Presentation, Interpretation, And Discussion Of Study Results

10.1 Presentation, Interpretation, and Discussion of the General Hypothesis Results

The general hypothesis was as follows: "The level of organizational excellence is high inside Ben Toubel Hospital in Mila."

To verify this hypothesis, we relied on the T-test for a single sample to determine the mean and compare it with the presumed mean for the study, and the following table shows the study results:

Table 04: Level of Organizational Excellence Inside Ben Toubel Hospital in Mila

Metric	Sample Size	Presumed Mean	Mean	Standard Deviation	Degrees of Freedom	T	Significance Level	Decision
Overall	47	40	44.94	6.625	46	47.209	0.000	Significant at 0.01

Statistical Reading of the Table

From Table 04, we obtained a mean for organizational excellence of 44.94, which is greater than the presumed mean of 40. We obtained a standard deviation of 6.625. To determine the significance of the difference in the level of organizational excellence at Ben Toubel Hospital in Mila from the doctors' perspective, we compared the presumed mean with the mean for organizational excellence, which was higher than the presumed mean.

Therefore, we can accept the general hypothesis that "Organizational excellence is high at Ben Toubel Hospital in Mila from the doctors' perspective," as affirmed by the T-value of 47.209, a positive value at a significance level of 0.000, statistically significant at the 0.01 level.

Discussion of the General Hypothesis Results

These results can be explained by the doctors' significant awareness of the importance of organizational excellence within the hospital. Their familiarity with the fundamental elements that drive them to develop their capabilities and skills and compete with other hospitals can only be achieved by applying principles of excellence within the hospital.

It is essential to focus on understanding the principles and dimensions of organizational excellence and conducting training courses and scientific seminars for all hospital staff to comprehend these principles and their importance for the hospital's survival and development.

Our study agrees with the studies by Ali Mohammed Said Al-Ali (2016), Reem Ahmad Saleh Al-Ghamdi (2018), Ruba Ezzat Al-Kanj (2020), Ahmed Jasim and Khalaf Taha (2022), and Reem Mohammed Al-Sheet and Asmaa Al-Khayyat (2023), where all studies concurred on the high level of organizational excellence.

10.2 Presentation, Interpretation, and Discussion of the First Partial Hypothesis Results

The first hypothesis was: "There are no statistically significant differences in the level of organizational excellence at Ibn Toubal Hospital from the perspective attributed to the gender variable."

To verify this hypothesis, we relied on Levene's test for homogeneity and the T-test for independent samples, with the following results:

Table 05: Results of the First Partial Hypothesis

Gender	Levene's Test for Homogeneity	Significance Level	Sample Size	Mean	Standard Deviation	Degrees of Freedom	T-Value	Significance Level	Decision
Male	0.173	0.680	6	51.00	7.071	45	2.289	0.013	Significant at 0.05
Female			41	44.05	6.033				

Statistical Reading of the Table

From Table 05, we see that Levene's test for homogeneity value was 0.173, a value not statistically significant at the alpha level of 0.05. This led us to use the F-test for two independent samples, where we obtained a mean of 51.00 for males compared to 44.05 for females.

The T-test value of 2.289 is not statistically significant at the alpha level of 0.05. This leads us to accept the null hypothesis that "There are no statistically significant differences between genders (male/female) in the level of organizational excellence," thus rejecting the hypothesis stating "There are statistically significant differences between genders (male/female) in the level of organizational excellence," with a 95% confidence interval and a 5% error probability.

Our current study differs from the study by Ahmed Jasim and Khalaf Taha (2022) regarding the existence of differences in the level of organizational excellence attributed to the gender variable (male/female).

Discussion of the First Hypothesis Results

The presentation above indicates that this hypothesis, which posited the existence of statistically significant differences in the level of organizational excellence among doctors attributed to gender (male/female), was not confirmed.

This result can be interpreted as due to the high intellectual level of doctors and their similar views on the concept of organizational excellence. They are aware of the most important procedures and management contributing to excellence, including leadership styles, communication methods, customer interaction, and addressing the hospital's specific deficiencies

This unifies doctors' perspectives on organizational excellence level regardless of their gender (male/female).

10.3 Discussion and Interpretation of the Second Partial Hypothesis Results

The second hypothesis stated: "There are no statistically significant differences in the level of organizational excellence at Ben Toubel Hospital from the perspective attributed to the specialization variable (general practitioner/specialist)." To verify this hypothesis, we relied on the Levene's test for homogeneity, and the results were as follows:

Table 06: Results of the Second Partial Hypothesis

Specialization	Levene's Test for Homogeneity	Significance Level	Sample Size	Mean	Standard Deviation	Degrees of Freedom	Decision
General	0.03	0.958	18	46.06	6.245	45	Significant at 0.05
Specialist			29	44.24	6.706		

Statistical Reading of the Table

From Table 06, we see that the Levene's test for homogeneity value was 0.03, which is statistically significant at the alpha significance level of 0.05. We obtained a mean value of 46.06 for general practitioners compared to 44.24 for specialists.

This leads us to reject the null hypothesis that "There are no statistically significant differences between doctors (general practitioner/specialist) in the level of organizational excellence," and consequently accept the alternative hypothesis that "There are statistically

significant differences between doctors (general practitioner/specialist) in the level of organizational excellence," with a 95% confidence interval and a 5% error probability.

Discussion of the Second Hypothesis Results:

The existence of differences in the level of organizational excellence from the doctors' perspective, favoring general practitioners, can be attributed to their constant interaction with hospital management and their familiarity with the ongoing management procedures.

It was observed that most general practitioners are involved in administrative responsibilities in addition to their medical duties, unlike specialists who do not have other responsibilities besides their medical tasks within the hospital, as well as their medical engagements in the private sector.

This explains the difference in the level of organizational excellence inside Ben Toubel Hospital from the doctors' perspective (general practitioner/specialist) in favor of general practitioners. This result agrees with the study by Reem Mohammed Al-Sheet and Asmaa Al-Khayyat (2023).

CONCLUSION

This field study aimed to assess the level of organizational excellence at Ben Toubel Hospital in Mila from the doctors' perspective, considering doctors as a key factor in achieving organizational excellence within hospitals and for their continued competitiveness. The study concluded the following results:

- The level of organizational excellence is high at Ben Toubel Hospital in Mila from the doctors' perspective.
- There are no statistically significant differences in the level of organizational excellence at Ben Toubel Hospital from the perspective attributed to the gender variable.
- There are statistically significant differences in the level of organizational excellence at Ben Toubel Hospital from the doctors' perspective attributed to the specialization variable (general practitioner/specialist).

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Encourage creative ideas in the hospital to create the necessary avenues for achieving excellence.
- Work on improving communication channels and trust levels with doctors to encourage them to provide all their skills to meet the requirements of excellence within the hospital.
- Urge hospital leadership to raise organizational excellence levels, relying on analyzing the internal and external environment of the hospital, identifying and addressing its weaknesses, and working on points that aid in development.
- Conduct more studies on organizational excellence in the healthcare sector due to its significant importance.

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